

New Directions in Pesticide Research, Development, Management, and Policy

1993

**New Directions in Pesticide Research,
Development, Management, and Policy**

November 1-3, 1993

Program and Presenters' Abstracts

**Virginia Water Resources
Research Center**

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COLLECTED ABSTRACTS
of the
FOURTH NATIONAL CONFERENCE ON PESTICIDES

**NEW DIRECTIONS IN PESTICIDE RESEARCH,
DEVELOPMENT, MANAGEMENT, AND POLICY**

November 1-3, 1993

**Hyatt Richmond
Richmond, Virginia**

Sponsored by

**Virginia Water Resources Research Center
Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University**

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- 9:00-9:45 am** **Opening — Ballroom A**
Victor Kimm, Acting Assistant Administrator, Office of Prevention, Pesticides, and Toxic Substances, U.S. Environmental Protection Agency
- 9:45-10:00 am** **ADJOURN for Session Meetings**

Session Meetings

November 1, 1993

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Ballroom C/D

Moderator: Marvin A. Lawson, Office of Pesticide Management, Virginia Department of Agriculture and Consumer Services, Richmond, VA

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 Water Environment Federation, Alexandria, VA

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Speaker: Michael Robinson, Director, National Zoo, Smithsonian Institute,
 Washington, DC; **Title:** *The Tropics as a Source of New Defenses Against Old Enemies*

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Moderator: Marvin A. Lawson, Office of Pesticide Management, Virginia Department of Agriculture and Consumer Services, Richmond, VA

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Moderator: Nancy Malloy, National Center for Food and Agriculture Policy, Washington, DC

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Moderator: Charles Finley, Jr., Virginia Forestry Association, Richmond, VA

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Moderator: Harry H. Gregori, Jr., Director, Policy and Planning and Public Affairs,
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Herbicides in Ohio's Drinking Water: Risk Assessment, Reductions, and Communication

D. B. Baker¹ and R. P. Richards¹

Quantitative data on herbicide concentrations in Ohio's public and private water supplies, coupled with data on the toxicity of these compounds, support the application of relative risk assessment to issues surrounding herbicide occurrence in this state's drinking water supplies. Exposure data indicate that less than 1 percent of Ohio's population consume drinking water containing herbicides at concentrations in excess of drinking water standards. Atrazine and alachlor are the two herbicides most likely to be found at concentrations above drinking water standards. Where standards are exceeded, it is by small amounts. Isolated private water supplies affected by point sources of groundwater contamination generally account for the highest herbicide exposure rates. The largest amounts of exposure, although at lower rates, occur in public water supplies using surface waters derived from intensively row-cropped watersheds.

Since drinking water standards include substantial safety factors, the most likely outcome of efforts to reduce herbicide exposures will be to increase the margin of safety, rather than to improve human health. Given such an outcome, herbicide exposure reduction programs should emphasize those management improvements that (1) have positive economic impacts on farmers, such as avoiding over-application of herbicides, (2) reduce point sources of herbicide contamination, or (3) indirectly reduce herbicide runoff while reducing runoff of sediments and phosphorus, as through adoption of conservation tillage. Since, for the vast majority of herbicides, the gap between exposures and toxicity is even wider than for atrazine and alachlor, concerns regarding synergistic interactions among herbicides appear unwarranted.

To support appropriate regulation and avoid over-regulation of herbicide use, the procedures of relative risk assessment need to be rigorously applied and the results communicated both to the general public and to policy makers. Ideally, these procedures should be applied to as broad a spectrum of possible drinking water contaminants as possible, so that efforts to improve human health by improving drinking water quality can be targeted to those pollutants where the greatest gains can be obtained per unit investment, whether it be in pollution prevention or in treatment.

¹Water Quality Laboratory, Heidelberg College, 310 E. Market St., Tiffin, OH 44883